

DETECTION OF HUMAN SKIN IN NEAR INFRARED HYPERSPECTRAL IMAGERY

Abel S. Nunez and Michael J. Mendenhall

Air Force Institute of Technology
Department of Electrical and Computer Engineering
2950 Hobson Way
WPAFB, OH 45433-7765

ABSTRACT

One of the difficulties in search and rescue missions is finding a small target, such as a person, in a large cluttered area. Airborne hyperspectral cameras are now being deployed to aid in this SAR mission. Motivated by the successes of such systems, we define a hyperspectral model of human skin in the visible and near infrared regions of the spectra so we can exploit knowledge gained during the modeling process to aid in human skin detection. Based on observations of the skin model results, an efficient and robust skin detection algorithm using channels in the near infrared region of the spectra is developed. Our algorithm is denoted the *Normalized Difference Skin Index*, motivated by the *Normalized Difference Vegetation Index* used in the literature for detecting vegetation in hyperspectral imagery. We demonstrate the capabilities of our skin detection methodology to detect skin amongst objects known to cause false detections for methodologies using three channel color data.

Index Terms— hyperspectral imagery, skin detection, skin modeling, search and rescue

1. INTRODUCTION

Detecting small targets in geographically large areas with a significant amount of background clutter is a difficult task. This is exactly the task of Search and Rescue (SAR) missions, where the targets of interest are people. Detection methods that exploit color imagery of the search area provide one way for locating lost persons [1], but are limited in capability. Hyperspectral data provides a diverse set of features that can possibly improve the successes in SAR, and are currently being exploited by the Civil Air Patrol (CAP) Airborne Real-Time Cueing Hyperspectral Enhanced Reconnaissance

The authors would like to thank Christina Schutte and Dr. Devert Wickert of the Air Force Research Laboratory Sensors Directorate for their support of this research. Special thanks to Dr. Heidi Bertram, Wright-Patterson Medical Center, Department of Pathology, for her consultation on this effort.

The views expressed in this article are those of the authors and do not reflect the official policy or position of the United States Air Force, Department of Defense, or the U.S. Government.

(ARCHER) system [2]. Data cubes collected by airborne hyperspectral cameras can be analyzed to determine if there is something in the image worthy of further investigation. It can be difficult, however, to quickly determine which pixels of the hyperspectral image are “background” and which ones are areas of interest to the SAR team. Using spectral signatures, one can locate missing persons or vehicles among the imagery, and dispatch rescue teams to those areas of interest. A simpler method for analyzing the hyperspectral images on the aircraft versus a ground station (as used in CAP ARCHER) could not only speed up the SAR process, but make aspects of this process easier.

The first step in detecting skin in a hyperspectral image is to understand skin reflectance. This is accomplished by way of modeling. Once a well defined model exists, one can change parameters to determine how reflectance changes based on different characteristics of the skin. Based on the observations, it is possible to create efficient algorithms for skin detection. This process is described in detail in the subsequent sections.

2. SKIN MODEL

2.1. Organization of tissue layers in human skin

Human skin in the near infrared (NIR) can be described as six layers made of dermal tissue with varying amounts of water and melanosomes. Each of these six layers transmits and reflects light depending on each layer’s absorption coefficient, reduced scattering coefficient, and thickness. Below the six layers of skin is a layer of subcutaneous fat with a large amount of reflectance in the NIR when sufficiently thick. Based on knowledge of the optical coefficients of each layer, the thickness of each layer, and the reflectance of subcutaneous fat, a model of skin reflectance can be defined.

Figure 1 (top) shows the absorption and reduced scattering coefficients for skin’s constituent components. The melanosome absorption decreases as wavelength increases. Water absorption has a general trend of increasing as wavelength increases with some variations. The reduced scattering coefficient of the dermal tissue decreases as wavelength

Fig. 1. (Top) Absorption coefficient for water (a_{water}), absorption coefficient for melanosomes (a_{mel}), and the reduced scattering coefficient for the dermis (s'_{dermis}) from 1000nm to 1500nm [3, 5, 6]. (Bottom) Reflectance of 18mm thick section of fat [4].

increases. The thickness and the water content of each skin tissue layer is presented in Table 1 from [3]. Figure 1 (bottom) shows the reflectance of an 18mm thick slice of pork fat in the NIR collected by a reflectometer [4]. This reflectance is used as an estimate for the reflectance of subcutaneous fat.

The absorption coefficient for each skin tissue layer is based on the absorption coefficients of water (a_{water}) and melanosomes (a_{mel}), and is dependent on the wavelength of incident light energy. Other skin chromophores, such as hemoglobin, bilirubin, and betacarotene, do not significantly effect the absorption in the NIR [7] and can be ignored. Each skin tissue layer is assumed to have a certain abundance of liquid water w_n and blood b_n . As such, water in the skin as

Table 1. Skin tissue layer parameters: 1) stratum corneum, 2) living epidermis, 3) papillary dermis, 4) upper blood net dermis, 5) reticular dermis, and 6) deep blood net dermis [3].

Layer (n)	\approx Depth (d)	Water (w)	Blood (b)	Mel. (v)
1	20 μm	5%	0%	0%
2	80 μm	20%	0%	1.5-40%
3	150 μm	50%	4%	0%
4	80 μm	60%	30%	0%
5	1500 μm	70%	4%	0%
6	80 μm	70%	10%	0%

well as water in the blood are assumed to affect all aspects of the model. Blood in the skin is assumed to be made up of 85% water with no other significant absorbers or scatters in the NIR [8]. The absorption coefficients for the skin tissue layers, where n is the layer index, are shown in Eqn. 1. It is important to note that the living epidermis is the *only* skin tissue layer assumed to contain melanosomes. The amount of melanosomes in this skin tissue layer, v_2 , varies from 1.5% for a very fair-skinned person to 40% for the most darkly pigmented person [9]. It is also important to note that there is no blood in the stratum corneum or living epidermis.

$$a_n(\lambda) = v_n a_{\text{mel}}(\lambda) + (w_n + .85b_n) a_{\text{water}}(\lambda) \quad (1)$$

The reduced scattering coefficient for each skin tissue layer is based on the amount of blood-free dermal tissue in the layer. The reduced scattering coefficient for each skin tissue layer is presented below in Eqn. 2.

$$s'_n(\lambda) = s'_{\text{dermis}}(\lambda)(1 - b_n) \quad (2)$$

2.2. Reflection at skin tissue layers

The Kubelka-Munk equations describe reflection and transmission of light at a specific wavelength in a homogenous layer of material with a constant thickness, where each layer absorbs and isotropically scatters the incident light energy. The transmission ($T_n(\lambda)$) and reflection ($R_n(\lambda)$) of light in the n^{th} skin tissue layer for wavelength λ is described in Eqn. 3 and Eqn. 4 respectively:

$$T_n(\lambda) = \frac{4\beta(\lambda)}{(1 + \beta(\lambda))^2 e^{K(\lambda)d_n} - (1 - \beta(\lambda))^2 e^{-K(\lambda)d_n}}, \quad (3)$$

$$R_n(\lambda) = \frac{(1 - \beta(\lambda))^2 (e^{K(\lambda)d_n} - e^{-K(\lambda)d_n})}{(1 + \beta(\lambda))^2 e^{K(\lambda)d_n} - (1 - \beta(\lambda))^2 e^{-K(\lambda)d_n}}, \quad (4)$$

where

$$\beta(\lambda) = \sqrt{a_n(\lambda)/(a_n(\lambda) + 2s'_n(\lambda))},$$

$$K(\lambda) = 2\sqrt{a_n(\lambda)(a_n(\lambda) + 2s'_n(\lambda))},$$

and d_n is the thickness of the skin tissue layer [10].

The Fresnel equation describes the amount of reflection at the interface between two materials with indices of refraction of n_1 and n_2 [3]:

$$F = \left(\frac{n_2 - n_1}{n_2 + n_1} \right)^2. \quad (5)$$

2.3. Reflectance model

Based on the amount of light reflected and transmitted from each skin tissue layer, Eqn. 6 describes a model of the reflectance of human skin as a function of wavelength. The values of R_n and T_n for values of $n = 1 \dots 6$ are generated from the Kubelka Munk equations. The value of R_7 comes from the reflectance of fat shown in Fig. 1.

The index of refraction of the stratum corneum, n_2 , is ≈ 1.5 [3] and the index of refraction of the atmosphere, n_1 , is ≈ 1 . For the air/stratum corneum interface, the amount of reflection, F is approximately 4%. The indices of refraction between the remaining skin tissue layers are very close and therefore the amount of reflection is insignificant and is not considered in this model.

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{I}(\lambda) = & I_o(\lambda)F \\ & + I_o(\lambda)(1 - F)R_1(\lambda) \\ & + I_o(\lambda)(1 - F) \sum_{m=2}^7 R_m(\lambda) \prod_{n=1}^{m-1} T_n^2(\lambda) \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

Our model does not take into consideration multiple reflections within skin tissue layers since it would dramatically increase model complexity. Our earlier analysis indicates these additional reflections do not change the reflected light energy significantly.

Figure 2 plots the reflectance spectrum generated from the skin model for wavelengths of 1000nm to 1500nm for three different melanosome levels in the living epidermis. As the melanosome level increases, the reflectance decreases at the shorter wavelengths while the reflectance at the longer wavelengths is not significantly affected. The local minima and maxima in the skin reflectance as well as the general trend of decreasing reflectance as wavelength increases are due to water absorption.

3. NORMALIZED DIFFERENCE SKIN INDEX

The Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI) is the most commonly used algorithm for the detection of vegetation in hyperspectral imagery [11]. Our skin detection algorithm in Eqn. 7 describes a *Normalized Difference Skin Index* (NDSI) and is motivated by the NDVI. The quantity $\hat{\rho}_i(\lambda)$ of Eqn. 7 is the estimated reflectance of the i^{th} pixel at wavelength λ . The NDSI and NDVI are similar in that they “look” for a sudden change in reflectance over a specific range in the spectrum. Like the NDVI, the NDSI values range from -1 to 1 with values close to 1 indicating the presence of skin. As indicated in the previous section, we use the reflectance at 1100nm and 1400nm as the inputs for the algorithm.

$$\gamma_i = \frac{\hat{\rho}_i(1100\text{nm}) - \hat{\rho}_i(1400\text{nm})}{\hat{\rho}_i(1100\text{nm}) + \hat{\rho}_i(1400\text{nm})} \quad (7)$$

Fig. 2. Modeled NIR reflectance spectrum of skin.

The NDSI has a range of values that correspond to the range of melanosome levels. According to the model results, the NDSI values range from 0.641 for the darkest skin to 0.742 for the fairest skin. As such, a value of 0.641 can be used as a threshold for deciding whether a pixel is skin based on the output of the NDSI algorithm. A linear regression of melanosome levels from 0 to 40% versus NDSI values is described by the line, $v_2 = -395.017\gamma_i + 294.029$. The NDSI may also be able to be used to estimate the melanosome level of the epidermis depending on the ability of the hyperspectral camera to accurately collect at the wavelengths of 1100nm and 1400nm.

4. DATA DESCRIPTION

Images for our experiments were collected using a NIR hyperspectral camera collecting radiance data in the range 900-1744 nm. The images are 512×512 pixels with 81 spectral bands collected in approximately 10.5 nm wavelength increments. Radiance values collected by the camera were converted to estimated reflectance using the empirical line method.

The scene used for our experiment (Fig. 3 top) consists of four hands with different levels of pigmentation, vegetation, and various materials that could be confused for skin in color imagery. Objects in the scene include soil in the bottom left with some grass growing out of it. Next to the soil is a red brick with a flesh-colored doll behind it. To the right of the brick is a brown leather boot with a tree branch and leaves inside of it. The brick and the boot are resting on top of a brown wicker basket. In the top left of the image are two pieces of wood. To the right of the wood is a strip of brown paper bag paper and a piece of brown cardboard.

Fig. 3. (Top) Image of test scene. (Bottom) Skin detection within test scene.

5. RESULTS

The NDSI skin detection results are presented in Fig. 3 (bottom) where detections are represented as black pixels. Note that “typical” falsely detected objects for color-based skin detection are correctly rejected in our method, as is in-scene objects containing liquid (dirt and vegetation). Furthermore, areas of minor shadowing do not cause false alarms (it is unclear at this time if heavy shadowing causes any issues).

6. CONCLUSION

This paper introduced a physics-based model that describes the reflectance of human skin. Analysis of the model provides a key observation regarding the relationship between the spectral response at 1100nm and 1400nm that leads to a computationally efficient skin detection algorithm. Although our model is promising, it is in its infancy and requires further investigation. Our current efforts involve extending the model into the visible part of the spectrum and adding depth to the current model by incorporating additional chromophores such as hemoglobin, bilirubin, and betacarotene, validating modeling parameters such as scattering and absorption coefficients, and studying the effects of pigmentation differences.

7. REFERENCES

- [1] J. Brand and J. Mason, “A comparative assessment of three approaches to pixel-level human skin-detection,” *Proceedings of 15th International Conference on Pattern Recognition*, vol. 1, pp. 1056–1059, Sep 2000.
- [2] B. Stevenson, R. O’Connor, W. Kendall, A. Stocker, W. Schaff, D. Alexa, J. Salvador, M. Eismann, K. Barnard, and J. Kershenstein, “Design and performance of the civil air patrol archer hyperspectral processing system,” S. S. Shen and P. E. Lewis, Eds., vol. 5806, no. 1. SPIE, 2005, pp. 731–742.
- [3] I. V. Meglinski and S. J. Matcher, “Quantitative assessment of skin layers absorption and skin reflectance spectra simulation in the visible and near-infrared spectral regions,” *Physiological Measurement*, vol. 23, pp. 741–753, 2002.
- [4] C. L. Tsai and J. M. Fouke, “Tissue composition by nir spectroscopy,” *Proceedings of the 16th Annual International Conference of the IEEE Engineering in Medicine and Biology Society*, vol. 2, p. 1002, 1994.
- [5] K. F. Palmer and D. Williams, “Optical properties of water in the near infrared,” *Journal of the Optical Society of America (1917-1983)*, vol. 64, pp. 1107–1110, 1974.
- [6] E. Salomatina, B. Jiang, J. Novak, and A. Yaroslavsky, “Optical properties of normal and cancerous human skin in the visible and near-infrared spectral range,” *Journal of Biomedical Optics*, vol. 11, no. 6, Nov/Dec 2006.
- [7] R. Anderson and J. Parrish, “The optics of human skin,” *Journal of Investigative Dermatology*, vol. 77, pp. 13–19, 1981.
- [8] A. Roggan, M. Friebel, K. Dorschel, A. Hahn, and G. Muller, “Optical properties of circulating human blood in the wavelength range 400–2500 nm,” *Journal of Biomedical Optics*, vol. 4, no. 1, Jan 1999.
- [9] E. Angelopoulou, “Understanding the color of human skin,” *Human Vision and Electronic Imaging VI*, vol. 4299, no. 1, pp. 243–251, 2001.
- [10] J. Dawson, D. Barker, D. Ellis, E. Grassam, A. Cotterill, G. Fisher, and J. Feather, “A theoretical and experimental study of light absorption and scattering by in vivo skin,” *Physics in Medicine and Biology*, vol. 25, no. 4, pp. 685–709, 1980.
- [11] R. Myneni, F. Hall, P. Sellers, and A. Marshak, “The interpretation of spectral vegetation indexes,” *IEEE Transactions on Geoscience and Remote Sensing*, vol. 33, no. 2, Mar 1995.